

Value Added Tax Reforms in India

Basil John Thomas¹ and Nisha Joseph²

¹Asst Professor in Business, Sur University College, Oman

&

Associate Lecturer in Business, University of Sunderland, UK

drbasiljt@gmail.com

²Assistant Professor in Computing, SAINTGITS College Engineering, India

nishasjoseph@gmail.com

Abstract: VAT is a general consumption tax assessed on the value added to goods and services. This new system of taxation was introduced by the government for helping common people, traders, industrialists and also for the collection of the actual revenue from the traders and consumers. VAT system had removed double taxation and reduced the tax burden of the consumers and hence provided uniformity of tax system followed in different states across the country. VAT which was introduced as a taxation system has had multiple effects on the economy such as state government, manufacturer, stockist, retailer and most importantly the consumer. Here an attempt is made in this paper to study the effect of implementation of VAT in Indian Context. The investigation has been done with the help of primary data collected from Consumers and Traders on a random basis. The study found that the total tax revenue collected by the state governments has shown a drastic increase of nearly 100% in the post VAT introduction years.

Key words: Sales Tax, Revenue, Manufactures, Traders, Consumers

1. Introduction

Value Added Tax is a general consumption tax assessed on the value added to goods and services*. It is a consumption tax because it is borne ultimately by a final consumer and not a charge on companies. It is charged as a percentage of prices, which means that the actual tax burden is visible at each stage in the production and distribution chain. It is collected fractionally. i.e., the tax is neutral, regardless of how many transactions are involved.

VAT is a system of indirect taxation and is meant to be in lieu of other indirect taxes such as excise duty, customs duty, sales tax, service tax etc. In the conventional system of indirect tax, due to excise duty, there has been a cascading effect on the price of the final product. In order to avoid such a cascading effect of taxation, the concept of VAT was created. Under VAT, the tax is not

levied on the entire selling price of the product, but only on the value addition made at each stage of manufacturing. So it is obvious that industries preferred to go towards VAT system of taxation, which the product can be sold at a lower price without adversely affecting profits.

2. Significance of the study

It is the right time to study the VAT based system followed throughout which was introduced almost before a decade. The new system was then introduced to curb all malpractices prevailed in the taxation system. Of course, if we opted for VAT in the late fifties, the tax scenario would not have created such insurmountable debt impasse. A detailed study on the VAT system implemented is highly essential for creating awareness among the traders and consumers.

Globally 136 countries have implemented VAT. Under the VAT system, the taxation method has come down to a 3-layered architecture from a 20-layered method. The essence of VAT is that tax is charged at all stages of production and distribution of goods, but with a provision for some mechanism enabling the dealer to set off the tax they have paid on their purchase of goods (input tax) against the tax they charge on their sales (output tax). Thus the tax burden in all production and distribution process finally rests on the final buyer. That is the consumer, who consumes the goods. And therefore, it is called as a "consumption tax."

The design of state level VAT has been worked out by the Empowered Committee through several rounds of discussion and striking a federal balance between the common points of convergence regarding VAT and flexibility for the local characteristics of the states. The mechanism of state level VAT can be illustrated below in Table 1 & 2.

Table 1. GST

State X → State X	Cost	Profit	Total (S.P)	VAT 12.5%	Invoice	Tax Credit	Payable To Govt:
A sells → B	100	-	100	12.50	112.50	-	12.50
B → C	100	10	110	13.75	123.75	12.50	1.25
C → D	110	10	120	15.00	135.00	13.75	1.25
D → E	120	10	130	16.25	146.25	15.00	1.25
							16.25

Here,

- 'A' is the manufacturer with in the state X,
- 'B' is the wholesaler,
- 'C' is the retailer,
- 'D' is the stockist,
- 'E' is the final consumer.

No tax credit is liable for manufacturer and consumer.
 A's input tax is 12.50.
 B's output tax is 12.50 and input tax is 13.75
 Tax credit is 12.50
 Govt gets tax Rs.16.25/-

Table 2. CST

State X → State Y	Cost	CST	Profit	Total (S.P)	VAT	Invoice	Tax Credit	Payable To Govt:
A sells B	100	4	-	104	-	104	-	4
B → C	104	-	10	114	14.25	128.25	-	14.25
C → D	114	-	10	124	15.50	139.50	14.25	1.25
D → E	124	-	10	134	16.75	150.75	15.50	1.25
								20.75

Here,

- 'A' is the manufacturer in State X
- 'B' is the wholesaler in Y,
- CST – 4%, (when CST paid, no VAT no tax credit)
- 'B' the wholesaler has no tax credit ,
- B's output tax is nil, in put tax is 14.25

awareness of the new system of taxation and also the dilemma concerned with accepting a change. In this context it is worthwhile to consider the factors like transparency, need of the consumers and the governance of VAT to study about the new system of taxation and to give valuable suggestions and recommendations.

3. Statement of the Problem

VAT was introduced by the government mainly to help common people, traders, industrialists and also the government. It was indeed a move towards more efficiency equal competition and fairness in the taxation system of the state. But the people and the traders were in a confusing state of mind to accept the concept of VAT. This may have been due to the lack of

4. Data and Methodology

The survey data for the present study was collected from 600 respondents constituting of consumers and traders/dealers through an opinion survey and personal interview. The sale and stock details were collected from selected traders on a random basis. The period of study is April 2016. Data have been collected and analysed with the help of statistical

tools like ANOVA (two way without replication), pie-charts, and suitable figures.

5. Review of Literature

Many studies have pointed out that one of the major reasons for lack of tax compliance as the complexity and cost of compliance due to statutory, procedural and other hassles. National Institute of Public Finance and Policy (NIPFP), New Delhi conducted studies on the system of VAT. Haryana was the first Indian state to have implemented VAT. Reports indicate that Haryana recorded a hike to the tune of 30% tax collection during the past 10 years

A study undertaken at the NIPFP in 1994 had observed: "The system (*of sales taxation*) that is operating at present is archaic, irrational and complex—according to knowledgeable experts the most complex in the world. It interferes with the free play of market forces, and competition, causes economic distortions, and entails high costs of compliance and administration.

6. Results and Discussions

6.1 State's Revenue

In order to assess the impact of VAT on central and state revenues the following methodology was adopted. Since it is generally recognised that the major part of tax base in any state within sales tax is manufacturing sector

output, with organized manufacturing contributing a giant's share, this exercise limits itself to exploring the impact taking the registered manufacturing sector as the base.

Taking the data published by Annual Survey of Industries (ASI) at the two-digit level as the basic data, an attempt is made to first segregate the taxed inputs and allow for tax credit for the same. Using this information with the information on total value of inputs (excluding service sector inputs as well as electricity, gas and water supply), one can compute a ratio for each industry group, of the proportion of taxed inputs to total material inputs. Applying this ratio to the value of material inputs, for each industry group, and using 4 per cent as the rate of tax on all inputs yields the amount of loss in revenue on account of tax rebate. The value of output correspondingly is adjusted downwards.

States get a share of taxes from the centre. The traditional devolution criteria like area, distance and population have not been favourable. The share of Central taxes as a proportion of total revenues has come down during the 1990s, especially after the Eleventh Finance Commission, which had to adopt substantially different standards for tax devolution. The share of central taxes to the total revenue of the state for the last 15 years indicated that the share increases gradually (Table 3 and Fig 1). The total revenue of the states also showed a steady increase.

Table 3. Share of central taxes to total revenue

Year	Share in central taxes	Total revenue	Percentage
'90-'91	43626	240293	20
'91-'92	57643	285212	20
'92-'93	68695	331873	21
'93-'94	103696	392205	19
'94-'95	83842	466642	18
'95-'96	103696	542356	19
'96-'97	124265	614508	20
'97-'98	127170	632490	20
'98-'99	138230	719812	19
'99-'00	153520	725945	21
'00-'01	158561	811495	20
'01-'02	161426	905639	18
'02-'03	171522	1063388	16
'03-'04	201200	1181536	17
'04-'05	240495	1350049	18
'05-'06	253251	1659646	15
'06-'07	302690	1914005	16

Source: Budget in brief

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Budget in brief

Table.3 and Figure.1 depicts the item wise distribution of states share on central taxes. This indicates that in the years after the implementation of VAT the states' share increased drastically compared to the preceding years.

6.2

Consumers

Consumers were classified in to three groups on the basis of their average purchase per month (Rs.500-1000; 1000-2000; 2000-3000) and designated as low, medium and high. 200 consumers were interviewed from each category and a questionnaire was given to the consumers for finding their awareness about VAT, their opinion about billing and hike in price due to VAT. Consumers are of opinion that the VAT introduced a 4 percent additional burden in their purchase. In most of the items there observe a 13 percent increase in price.

6.2.1 Awareness

Regarding the awareness of consumers (Table 4 and Fig 2) about VAT, 70 percent of the consumers under the low group , 45 percent under medium group and 65 percent under high group were not heard of VAT.

Table 4. Consumers opinion about the awareness of VAT

Groups	Opinion			
	Yes		No	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
500-1000	60	30	140	70
1000-2000	110	55	90	45
2000-3000	70	35	130	65
Total	240	41.67	360	58.33

Source: Survey data

Ho : All consumers are not aware of VAT

Chi square test with the null hypothesis gives 1.437 as test value indicated that the all the consumers were not at all aware of VAT.

Source: Survey data

6.2.2 Billing

Regarding the intend of billing for the items they have purchased at every time the middle group was more (75%) in need of bill. They opined that the need bill for future servicing in the home appliances and reporting the defect etc. in the provisions, especially in packed goods, in future (Table 5 and Fig 3). In total half (50%) of the consumers were not needed the bill but the rest 50% were in need of the bill.

Table 5. Consumers opinion about the billing

Groups	Opinion			
	Yes		No	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
500-1000	70	35	130	65
1000-2000	150	75	50	25
2000-3000	80	40	120	60
Total	300	50	300	50

Source: Survey data

Ho: All the consumers were not intended to have bill for their purchase

The test indicated that the low chi-square value (0.000214) accepts the hypothesis that all the consumers were not in need of bill for their every purchase. Most of the consumers (60 percent) opined that they spend more time (more than that their time for selection of goods) in the market for billing.

Source: Survey data

6.2.3 Hike in Price

Majority of the consumers (92%) were of opinion that there is increase in the price of goods in the recent years. But they cannot able to isolate the reason for the same. Majority of all category of purchase group blame government and authority for this hike in price (Table 6 & Table 7).

Table 6. Opinion of consumers about increase in price

Groups	Opinion			
	Yes		No	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
500-1000	180	90	20	10
1000-2000	200	100	0	0
2000-3000	190	95	10	5
Total	570	95	30	5

Source: Survey data

Table 7. Opinion of consumers about reason for increase in price

Groups	Opinion*							
	Government				Dealers			
	Yes		No		Yes		No	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
500-1000	100	50	20	10	80	40	0	0
1000-2000	120	60	20	10	40	20	20	10
2000-3000	90	45	30	15	80	40	00	0
Total	310	51.67	70	11.67	200	33.33	20	3.33

Source: Survey Data, Neutral were added to "no"

4.3 Dealers

Fig 4. Indicates the opinion of dealers about the VAT impact. They are of the opinion that the workload has increased by 44 percent than the non-VAT years. The number of bills and amount included in the bill has also showed an increase by 33 and 23 percent respectively.

Source: Survey data

4.3.1 Analysis of variances

Opening stock of supermarkets was compared for obtaining the variation in their stock before and after VAT years. The null hypothesis is that there is no variation in the samples. The present study indicated that the variation in the stock after VAT was arisen due to chance. The difference in opening stock was insignificant and it supports the null hypothesis (Table 8).

Table 8. Comparison of effective stock of three super markets before and after VAT.

Shops	Opening stock lakhs			
	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16
1	18.7	20.5	24.5	28.65
2	28.27	30.72	35.67	46.32
3	12.75	15.85	18.35	32.87
<i>P-value</i> 0.175604				
<i>F crit</i> 4.06618				
<i>F</i> 2.123				

Source: Survey data

Ho: There is no variation in the samples

H1: There is variation in the samples

The Table 8. Indicates that there is no significant variation observed after Analysis of variance (two way ANOVA without replication) and the H0 is accepted.

The comparison of sale of supermarkets before and after VAT has been carried out in Table 9. The null hypothesis is that there is no variation in the sales before and after VAT. The present study indicates that the variation in the sale after VAT has arisen due to chance. The difference in sale was insignificant and it supports the null hypothesis.

Table 9. Comparison of effective sale of three super markets before and after VAT.

Shops	Sale in Lakhs			
	2003-04	2004-05	2005-06	2006-07
1	44.84	48.75	54.53	69.24
2	89.25	92.42	119.7	140.86
3	49.05	52.52	65.48	81.45
<i>F criti.</i> 4.066				
<i>F</i> 0.844				
<i>P</i> 0.50686				

Source: Survey data

H0: There is no variation in the sales before and after VAT

H1: There is variation in the sales before and after VAT

The table indicate that there is no significant variation observed after Analysis of variance (two way ANOVA without replication) and the H0 is accepted.

7. Conclusion and Implications

The study reveals that the state economy has received a tremendous boost on account of the implementation of VAT. VAT has enabled the Government in increasing its revenue and thereby promoting public welfare and benefit. It has also given adequate sealing against the malpractices done by the manufacturers, whole salers and the retailers. There is definitely got scope for further study in the subject and can give more results and benefits to the state as a whole and to its valuable

consumers. The following findings are gathered from the study on the impact of implementation of VAT.

1. The total tax revenue collected by the Kerala state government has shown a drastic increase of nearly 100% in the post VAT introduction years.
2. The effects of VAT have been negligible on the overall operational efficiencies and profit of these units.
3. From the perspective of the consumers, VAT has resulted in the increase in prices of certain goods and the overall burden of VAT can be summarised as 4% increase in prices.
4. VAT has resulted in greater transparency at all levels in maintenance of financial records starting from manufacturer upwards to the dealer. This is also one of the reasons for the increase in tax revenue of the state and prevention of tax evasion.
5. VAT as taxation regime has been able to put a stop on the practice of double

taxation in the whole value addition cycle of any product.

6. Due to the implementation of VAT, the dealers are forbidden to keep/maintain unaccounted stock and transactions. All transactions are required to be properly accounted and tax to be collected and paid for the same.
7. It is ascertained from this study that 70% of the consumers under low group, 45% of the consumers under the medium group and 65% of the consumers under high group were not having any proper awareness about VAT.
8. It is revealed that only 50% of the consumers demand bill for each transaction and they retain the bill for further queries.
9. Consumers are of the opinion that there is hike in price for goods on introduction of VAT and are not able to isolate the reason for the same.

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